

Omnichannel Business Strategy for MSME to Increase Profit during Post-Pandemic: A Case of Jaya Raya Store

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to analyze business issue of Jaya Raya Store as one of the MSME in Indonesia during post-pandemic, determining what kind of channel can be beneficial, how the channels proposed work well, determining the possible combination of channels as strategies to solve the business issue. The business issue was identified by using 5 why analysis and this study was made by using quantitative data obtained through distributing questionnaire surveys to 203 potential customers of Jaya Raya Store. The data is then analyzed by using regression analysis through SPSS statistics. Result of the research shows that for the business to keep improving especially during post-pandemic, expanding business channels is necessary and it is proofed that some channels such as phygital, digital promotions and digital catalogs have a great influence on customer awareness and their purchase decision. This study has the value that can be seen form the interesting strategies which can also be used for other business that experience the same business issues as Jaya Raya Store. The author has researched through channels as the variables of this study and provided four business solutions with implementation plan proposed for 1 year period. Business stakeholders need to focus on expanding the business channels so that more potential customers can be reached. This study discussed on four variables as the solutions such as phygital, digital promotions, social media, and digital catalog. The findings of this study can be a consideration for other business stakeholder to choose the best strategy for their business and it can be used for those who agree by applying the proposed business solutions and implementation plan to influence the potential customer awareness and their purchase decision.

KEYWORDS: Customer Awareness, MSMEs, Omnichannel, Purchase Decision.

INTRODUCTION

The impact of the Covid-19 pandemic in Indonesia has involved various business sectors, some are growing, some are permanent, and some are experiencing a drastic decline, especially the impact on the MSME sector since April 20. The number of MSME in Indonesia has reached 64.19 million in May 2021, which is also 99.92% of the entire business sector in Indonesia, which has felt different negative impacts from the Covid-19 pandemic. In an economic crisis situation like this, the MSME sector really needs to pay more attention to their business because of changing market conditions during and after the pandemic. Most people are very careful about managing their financial spending because of the uncertainty when this pandemic will end. This causes a decline in people's purchasing power for consumer goods and puts pressure on business businesses in Indonesia, especially the MSME sector. The existence of this pandemic has caused a decline in performance from the demand side (consumption and purchasing power of the people) which ultimately has an impact on the supply side, namely layoffs and the threat of default in credit payments (Bahtiar & Saragih, 2020).

Economic problems in Indonesia are also increasingly widespread with the Large-Scale Social Restrictions (PSBB) policies implemented in several regions in Indonesia. Referring to the Regulation of the Minister of Health No. 9/2020 concerning PSBB Guidelines in the context of Accelerating the Handling of Covid-19, PSBB includes restrictions on certain activities of residents in an area suspected of being infected with Covid-19 including restrictions on the movement of people and/or goods for a particular province or district/city to prevent the spread of Covid-19. These restrictions are at least carried out through school and work holidays, restrictions on religious activities, and/or restrictions on activities in public places or facilities. It is feared that with the PSBB, economic activities, especially production, distribution, and sales will experience disruptions which will ultimately contribute to the performance of MSME (Saturwa et al., 2021).

Before Pandemic Covid -19 started, Jaya Raya Store was doing well in their business with stable monthly income and slowly increasing. The issue started when the pandemic Covid-19 started which caused the store to be closed for 14 months to prevent the spread of the virus until May 2021 when the owner received the vaccine for the first time, and they started to open the store again.

Jaya Raya Store decided to re-open its store in May 2021, but there are some differences that are felt by shop owners that there is a decrease in customers coming to the store from before the pandemic, such as a decrease in the number of customers who come to the store than usual and differences in behavior. Customers where there are several customers who ask a lot about a product, but after that they immediately check the price of the product at other online stores and ask for a cheaper price. Of course, the seller cannot give such a cheap price because there is a cost that needs to be considered in every item sold. The customers are showing signs of what we call "showrooming" by starting to compare the prices of the online market which tend to be cheaper than buying directly at the outlet store. This has become an issue for Jaya Raya Store because all customers who do showrooming will cancel their purchases because of the price difference and the owner is afraid that they will lose the customer's trust to buy goods at Jaya Raya Store again.

Literature Review and Hypotheses Development

Omnichannel Strategy

Ellie Hickman et al. (2019) define omnichannel as an approach that arises when a business responds to changes in the nature of customers who change from one channel to a particular channel. Therefore, some businesses try to switch from one channel to another in order to stay competitive and reach a wider customer segment than usual. Omnichannel increases the use of digital devices in a business, so that the business can focus and build a more integrated customer approach for the business operations. (Hickman, Kharouf, & Sekhon, 2019). In relation to creating an experience for consumers to shop on an omnichannel strategy, the omnichannel strategy is influenced by factors such as brand awareness, perceived value, and Technology Readiness and there are three main channels in implementing the omnichannel strategy, namely in offline, online and digital stores (Hickman, Kharouf, & Sekhon, 2019).

According to the result of previous research measuring effectiveness of omnichannel retailing by Boora & Kiran (2018), the study shows a positive relationship between omnichannel strategy and business performance in the context of sales record and consumer behavior, promoting factors that promote the business can be more effective to attract customers. They also suggested through the research journal that organized retailers are successful if we can prioritize the promoting factors of the business omnichannel strategy.

Phygital

Phygital is a combination of real-life marketing and online strategy that enables business to use digital technology-based knowledge to enrich the user experience in online shopping and provide convenience for business people and customers themselves that makes it easier for Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSME) to carry out product marketing strategies in a wider range (Ernanto B, 2022). The author feels that phygital is the most appropriate solution for Jaya Raya Store after seeing the condition where Jaya Raya Store only has 1 offline store as their channel. There are so many businesses that have already used online platforms to sell and get very good results because in addition to increasing sales, these businesses can also get new prospective customers with a wider segment.

According to Pastezeur (2017), the physical and digital approach is almost non-existent for millennials where 82% of them access products through both offline stores and the internet. Combination of both the physical and digital approach could create a new experience that impacts the business and for that reason this combination is already applied by many businesses all around the world. Previous research reveals that customer experience will become the main issue for the business, so we need to understand the typologies and components in order to create the most effective and unique customer experience (Batat, 2018). Cesconi, F., & Franzoni, G. P. (2020) explained that measuring the phygital transformation started from identifying what needed to be measured, the target customers and setting expectations. They also mentioned that there are dimensions of measurement needed such as the customer operational dimension (customer interactions), business operational dimension (customer needs fulfillment), and dimension of customer satisfaction of their buying process journey.

Digital Promotions

Digital Promotions or what is commonly called digital marketing is a marketing strategy through digital media or the internet online. The concept of digital marketing is to boost product sales from a brand by utilizing technological advances. The number of digital marketing services used by companies, proves that this method has many advantages and benefits that can be obtained. In terms of costs, digital marketing can be implemented at a cost other than being cheaper than traditional marketing, not only that, this digital promotion channel also has other advantages which can branding more quickly, widely, and accurately (Idris M, 2022).

By applying digital promotions, MSME can reach a wider and larger segment as the target market of the business faster and can be applied with manageable budget (Saputra et al., 2021). In order to be attractive to get customer awareness, digital promotions, and increase profit, it is important to be better than competitors in marketing the business (Herhausen et al., 2020). The author realized after phygital, the result will be even better if it is supported by digital promotions which could attract customers in more effective and efficient ways than traditional marketing.

The concept of digital promotions in a simple explanation means marketing the products and services to increase sales, attract customers, and retain customers through digital platforms and technologies that have unlimited potential with the internet (Ghahremani Nahr et al., 2021). Some digital promotion channels provide objective and quantitative metrics through web analytics that help in strategic decision making where the result will be depending on the budget of the business and data accuracy. (Saura et al., 2017). This has to be measured subjectively in order to find out the result of customer orientation (Kyal et al., 2022).

Social Media

Now that almost everyone has their own social media, social media also plays an important role in running the company's business. Social media also now has various kinds with users of each social media who are from different segments. There are so many things that are used from social media, such as increasing brand awareness, seeing feedback and even being able to analyze competitors through this channel (Firdiansyah A, 2022). The author thinks that since social media is a very common thing nowadays, Jaya Raya Store need to have one for themselves because by being an up-to-date business, Jaya Raya Store is expected to be able to increase its revenue in line with increasing customer awareness of the product and the store.

According to Will Cannon (2021), measuring the social media preference for the omnichannel strategy can be done by identifying key social marketing channels preference from the customer, building the business personal branding in the social media and starting to engage prospective customers to reach a wider segment. Mariani et al. (2018) described 3 metrics of social media such as generic engagement, user engagement and brand engagement which are being calculated by assessing them into different interaction actions through underlying activities of liking, sharing, or commenting.

Digital Catalog

Digital catalog is one of the product marketing channels which utilizes technology and the internet to distribute product information more easily and quickly. The development of the digital catalog of every business should be seen as an opportunity by business owner. Through digital catalogs, businesses can reach more customers, provide a better shopping experience for customers and also facilitate collaboration with various parties because of the completeness and neatness of the catalog they have (Midtrans, 2021). The use of digital catalogs can also be profitable for Jaya Raya Store because they can be made without incurring large costs without financing for paper and ink such as physical catalogs.

According to Publitas research (2014) by looking at the demographics about gender distribution of digital catalog users mostly come from female users in around 61% of total users. By looking at the interest of digital catalog users, shopping digital catalog is the most interesting category and followed by news and sports catalog. We can also find out the information about traffic distribution per device category, average customer visit duration, when digital catalog viewed the most, and other customer preferences of accessing the digital catalog.

Customer Awareness

According to the Cambridge dictionary, customer awareness is when potential customers are aware of a business and the products it offers. As potential customers know information about what products are being sold and what solutions are offered by a business, this can also be interpreted as customer awareness. In order to increase customer awareness, we must be able to reach customers directly without intermediaries, such as by using a communication platform so that we can reach customers directly (Layuardi, 2021). The use of various channels in business can be considered to be crucial in order to increase customer awareness. According to Siddique & Hossain (2018), customer awareness will be connected to the customer recognition of a product and recalling the product they might remember. The previous study mentioned that customer awareness is connected with customer product usage history (Sharma & Trivedi, 2016)

Purchase Decision

Fandy Tjiptono (2016) defined the purchase decision as when the customer has to make a decision of choices when they are about to buy a product or services. Purchase decision can also be defined as an attitude when purchasing a product or services when the

customer has to select more than 1 choice and the decision has to be made (Schiffman and Kanuk, 2015). The decision will be influenced through the process while deciding on which one to purchase. According to Kotler and Armstrong (2017), purchase decisions are about a customer's decision to buy a product from a brand they choose and during the decision-making process, there will be two or more alternatives to be considered before finally choosing the best one.

According to Kotler (2018), there are 3 factors to be considered in order to determine customer purchase decisions which are product stability, customer behavior in buying products, and recommendations to purchase the products and while making the purchase decision, the customer will go through process started from identification, searching for information, product alternatives evaluation to be considered, making the purchase decision and lastly there will be behavior after purchasing the product (Kotler, 2017).

Based on the literature above, the conceptual framework can be shown as the figure below.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

As shown from the conceptual framework above, the first framework in the box on the left there are 4 independent variables that will be proposed as a solution for this research which are Phygital, Digital Promotions, Social Media, and Digital Catalog. At the end of the conceptual framework will display the dependent variables as the results to be achieved from the solutions proposed by the author which are expected to attract customer awareness. The second framework also has the exact same independent variable and what makes it different is that this second framework has the dependent variable on the customer's purchase decisions. If it has been realized, the two dependent variables are expected to be a solution that answers the problems that Toko Jaya Raya has.

METHOD

This research is supported by data obtained from a survey conducted by the author and the results of the survey indicate which one has the greatest effect on customer awareness, and their purchase decisions. The author hopes that with this data, we will get data about the most effective channel for Jaya Raya Store. This research design carried out by the author described as follows:

Table 1. Research Design

Research Design		
No.	Step	Desc.
1	Problem Exploration	This research Started from the problem statement as the first step. The author interviewed the owner of Jaya Raya Store and ask everything related to find the business issue.
2	Research Objectives Definition	After the business issue have been collected, research objectives were found and defined which narrow author's focus on this research and then everything summarized through 5 whys analysis to find out the root cause and to get the best solution for Jaya Raya Store.

3	Data Collection	Through this step, the author made a survey to collect data from the potential customers of Jaya Raya Store which result will support the effectiveness of each proposed solution in the conceptual framework.
4	Business Solutions	After the author went through all the step before, all the issues were solved and the best omnichannel strategies were formulated.
5	Implementation Plan	As the last step of this research, the author proposed the implementation plan for Jaya Raya Store.

Primary data of this research was collected through necessary questionnaires. This kind of data is needed for this research to find out information related to Jaya Raya Store and any data necessary for supporting the proposed business solution. The author interviewed the owner of Jaya Raya Store to collect data about the business and for the author to be able to visualize the business issue experienced by Jaya Raya Store more clearly because any questions that the author wants to ask for the purposes of this research answered directly through the interview. Questionnaires spread through random customer of Jaya Raya Store as the respondent with criteria as follows:

Table 2. Research Respondent Criteria

Criteria	Desc.	
	Existing Customer	Potential Customer
Domicile	Jabodetabek	Jabodetabek
Age	10-50 Years old	18-40 Years Old
Ever bought electronics products	Yes	Yes
Ever shop online	Yes/No	Yes

According to Sugiyono (2020), The research method with surveys is research carried out using questionnaires as a research tool carried out on small or large populations, but the data studied are data from samples taken from the population, so that relative incidence, distribution, and relationship between variables, sociology, and psychology. The purpose of this survey research is to provide a detailed description of the background, characteristics, and characteristics of a case or event of a general nature by using quantitative research method.

Sugiyono (2020) defined quantitative methodology research method as a research method based on the positive philosophy, used to examine the population of a particular sample, data collection using research tools, quantitative or statistical data analysis with the aim of testing the established research hypothesis. The research was conducted using a quantitative research method because the data needed to support this research is in the form of numbers shown in the form of visual graphics which are the result of calculating and measuring the value of each variable. The quantitative data obtained through questionnaires for this research aims to determine customer channel preferences, their awareness and their purchase decision.

Table 3. Survey Questionnaire

No.	Variable	Code	Questions
1	Phygital	P1	I want the products sold at Jaya Raya Online Store also being sold at the offline store
		P2	I want the Jaya Raya online store to display the updated stock of items that are also sold at the Jaya Raya offline store
		P3	I want the Jaya Raya online store to display the updated stock of products sold at the Jaya Raya offline store

		P4	I am happy if buyers can pick up their bought products directly at the Jaya Raya offline store even though they shop online
		P5	I am happy if purchased products online can be returned with clear evidence if something goes wrong with the products
		P6	I am happy if the Jaya Raya online shop provides a variety of payment methods such as Ovo, Gopay, Bank Transfer, Dana, etc.
2	Digital Promotions	DP1	I like to see digital promotions that have attractive image/video designs
		DP2	I am happy with digital promotions related to discounts
		DP3	I am happy with digital promotions related to cashback
		DP4	I am happy with digital promotions related to free shipping
3	Social Media	SM1	I want Jaya Raya Store's social media accounts to upload posts about product information being sold
		SM2	I want Jaya Raya Store's social media account to upload posts about current promos
		SM3	I want Jaya Raya Store's social media accounts to provide education about electronic goods
		SM4	I want Jaya Raya Store's social media accounts to actively reply to chats during working hours
4	Digital Catalog	DC1	I want Jaya Raya Store to provide a complete and informative digital catalog of its products
		DC2	I want Jaya Raya Store's digital catalog to display product photos clearly
		DC3	I want Jaya Raya Store's digital catalog to be easily accessible to all devices
		DC4	I want Jaya Raya Store to always provide the latest digital catalog
5	Customer Awareness	CA1	I like to check promos every week on social media, Tokopedia, Shopee, etc.
		CA2	I am constantly checking the media for new products I might find useful
		CA3	Sales admin from Shopee, Tokopedia, etc. can be my source of product information
		CA4	Influencers from Youtube, TikTok, etc. can be my source of product information
6	Purchase Decision	PD1	I always find out about the product information being promoted before making a decision to buy
		PD2	I always consult with friends or family about the product I want to buy before making a decision to buy it
		PD3	I always compare a product with other products before making a decision to buy
		PD4	Price is an important factor for me in making a decision to buy a product
		PD5	The quality of goods is an important factor for me in making a decision to buy a product

After the author conducted the survey, the data obtained would be in the form of quantitative data which would later be processed and tested through IBM SPSS as the tools used by the author in conducting statistical analysis. The author will start by proving the feasibility of the data through validity and reliability tests. After the data has been proven valid and reliable, the data will be used

again to find the regression in order to prove that there is a regression from the independent variables to the dependent variable in the conceptual framework in chapter 2 so that the author can later provide more accurate and precise business solutions.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Result and Analysis

Based on the data obtained through the survey of 203 respondents who meet the criteria to fill in the questionnaire, the result will be helpful for the author to finish this research. The survey result stated as below:

Table 4. Respondent Profile

Demographic	Level	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	143	70.4
	Female	60	29.6
Age	18-30	129	63.5
	31-40	59	29.1
	41-50	14	6.9
	>51	1	0.5
Domicile	Jakarta	143	70.4
	Tangerang	36	17.7
	Bekasi	9	4.4
	Depok	7	3.4
	Bogor	5	2.5
	Bandung	2	1
Jobs	Private company employee	119	58.6
	Entrepreneurs	49	24.1
	Students	25	12.3
	State-owned enterprise employee	3	1.5
	Others	7	3.5
Monthly Income	< Rp 2.000.000	6	3
	Rp 2.000.000 - Rp 5.000.000	23	11.3
	Rp 5.000.000 – Rp 8.000.000	98	48.3
	>Rp 8.000.000	78	37.4

According to the survey result of 203 respondents above, the author found out about the respondent profile that is different to one another. After the demographics section, the survey will go into the questions section to test the conceptual framework variables which include phygital, digital promotions, social media, and digital catalog which the result shown as table below.

Table 5. Respondent Interest Percentage

Survey Question	Respondent Interest Scale Percentage				
	1	2	3	4	5
P1	0	0	6.9	60.1	33
P2	0	0	3.4	50.2	46.3
P3	0	0	5	55	40.1
P4	0.5	1	4.5	49.5	44.6
P5	0	0	4.4	50.7	44.8
P6	0	0	3.4	38.4	58.1
DP1	0	0.5	18.2	46.3	35.0

DP2	0	0	11.3	37.4	51.2
DP3	0.5	2	17.7	44.8	35
DP4	0	0	11.3	38.9	49.8
SM1	0	2.5	18.7	45.4	33.5
SM2	0	1	13.8	39.9	45.3
SM3	0	2	14.8	46.8	36.5
SM4	0	1	12.8	40.4	45.8
DC1	0	1	24.6	41.9	32.5
DC2	0	1	20.2	41.9	36.9
DC3	0	1	18.7	47.3	33
DC4	0	1	18.2	44.3	36.5
CA1	4.4	13.3	24.6	35.5	22.2
CA2	4.0	11.4	26.2	30.7	22.7
CA3	0.5	6.9	20.2	42.9	29.6
CA4	1	4.4	23.6	39.9	31
PD1	0	0	7.4	43.0	49.8
PD2	0.5	0.5	10.4	38.6	50
PD3	0	0	8.4	43.3	48.3
PD4	0	0	4.5	38.1	56.9
PD5	0	0	5.4	37.9	56.7

The data obtained through the survey of 203 respondents will be tested for the validity and reliability of the data by using SPSS Statistics. After the data already passed the validity and reliability test, then the author chooses the regression analysis to measure the value of one independent variable to the dependent variable. Validity test is a test that is used to measure whether or not a questionnaire is valid and the questionnaire can be said to be valid if the questions on the questionnaire are able to reveal something to be measured by the questionnaire or if the test carries out its measuring function or provides precise and accurate measurement results according to for the purpose of carrying out the test. In this validity test first of all, the author must input all data from the questionnaire results to be tested for validity. The quantitative data showed positive feedback due to the validity test.

After the author is done with the validity test, the author continues to start the reliability test to test and to obtain information that can be used reliably as a data collection tool and able to reveal actual information in the field. A questionnaire can be considered to be reliable if one's answers to statements are consistent or stable from time to time. High and low reliability, empirically indicated by a number called the value of the reliability coefficient. High reliability is indicated by an r value close to 1. Generally agreed that reliability is considered satisfactory if ≥ 0.700 . This reliability test will be discussed one by one of each variable from the conceptual framework which are phigital, digital promotions, social media, digital catalog, customer awareness and purchase decision.

Table 6. Reliability Analysis

Variables	No. of Items	Cronbach's Alpha	Reliability
Phyigital	6	.899	Very Good
Digital Promotions	4	.843	Very Good
Social Media	4	.914	Very Good
Digital Catalog	4	.962	Very Good
Customer Awareness	4	.916	Very Good
Purchase Decision	5	.913	Very Good

After the author is done with the reliability test, the author decided to choose the regression instead of correlation because if we look at the framework, the purpose of this research survey is to find out the relationship that the independent variable on the left side of the framework has to the dependent variable as the outcome and not the correlation of each variable. In order for us to find

out which of the independent variables has the best outcome to be accepted by the dependent variable, the t-score (t) needs to be higher than 1.96 point and the significant point (sig.) needs to be smaller than .05 point.

Table 7. Regression Analysis to Customer Awareness

Model	Unstandardized Coefficient		Standardized coefficient	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
Phygital	.15	.140	.055	.751	.453
Digital Promotions	.197	.124	.130	1.587	.114
Social Media	.174	.111	.128	1.563	.120
Digital Catalog	.324	.099	.258	3.287	.001

According to the regression result above, we can see that phygital, digital promotions, and social media do not meet the criteria to pass this regression test because the phygital got .751 point for the t-score which is smaller than 1.96 point and got .453 point for the significant point which is bigger than .05 point. Digital promotions also do not meet the requirements because the t score only gets 1.587 point which is smaller than 1.96 point and .114 point for the significant point which is higher than .05 point. Social media can not be accepted as well because the t-score only got 1.563 point which is smaller than 1.96 point and for the significant point only got .120 point which is higher than .05 point. Although the three variables above are can not be accepted for the customer awareness variable regression, the fourth variable which is digital catalog can be accepted because it got 3.287 point for the t-score which is higher than 1.96 point and it got .001 point for the significant point which is smaller than .05 point. From this result, it is can be considered in line with wang (2016) that with MSME business stakeholders will have to be prepared and be flexible in upgrading the business due to the fast changing business environment.

Table 8. Regression Analysis to Purchase Decision

Model	Unstandardized Coefficient		Standardized coefficient	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
Phygital	.303	.084	.260	3.604	.000
Digital Promotions	.176	.075	.189	2.358	.019
Social Media	.129	.067	-.156	-1.938	.054
Digital Catalog	.218	.059	.282	3.679	.000

Looking at the figure above, the regression to dependent variable of purchase decision have a different outcome than the customer awareness before. The independent variables that can be accepted are phygital, digital promotions, and digital catalog. We can see that the phygital variable can be accepted because its t-score reached 3.604 point which is higher than 1.96 point and it has .000 significant point which is smaller than .05 point. The digital promotion can also be accepted because it has 2.358 t-score points which is higher than 1.96 point and .000 significant point which is smaller than .05 point. Digital catalog can also be accepted as well because it has 3.679 t-score point which is higher than 1.96 point and a significant point of .000 which is smaller than .05 point. Although three of the variables above can be accepted, social media is the only one that cannot be accepted this time because it has -1.938 t-score point which is smaller than 1.96 point and it has .054 significant point which is slightly higher than .05 point. This research has proven the Karadag (2017) research to be make sense that the level of the business matters and has a significant effect to MSMEs.

From the 2 regression result of customer awareness and purchase decision above, it is proven that there are influence from digital catalog over customer awareness and also influence from phygital, digital promotions and digital catalog over the customer purchase decision so to continue the research the author can make the best strategy as a solution for Jaya Raya Store

Business Solution

Advertise with Digital Catalog Through Digital Platform

According to the regression analysis of customer awareness dependent variable, Digital catalog will be the only channel to be effective to the customer awareness. Considering that one of the components of the promotion mix is advertising, advertising is a paid promotion service and is one of the most common promotional tools used by a business in conveying information about the products it sells and is able to increase interest and interest from potential customers who see the advertisement.

Along with today's technological developments, advertising is now generally done digitally. Through digital platforms, every business is able to disseminate information about products that are widely offered more efficiently and effectively. The author thought of one strategy by advertising the product of Jaya Raya Store through digital catalog banners posted through possible digital platforms such as Tokopedia TopAds, Shopee Ads, Facebook Ads, Google Ads, TikTok Ads, etc.

In advertising with a digital catalog, you will need at least a banner containing the products that people are most interested in with photos, a brief description and the price of the product. If we can make an attractive design, that would be great because it will definitely be of added value to potential customers who see the advertisement.

The most important thing before we are going to advertise our product, we need to make sure first that our business digital platform is ready to be visited by a lot of people. Whether it is social media or online shop or offline shop, we have to make sure that after the potential customer sees the advertisement, they can know where to find us.

Sign Up for Every Possible Digital Platform Marketplace

According to the regression analysis of purchase decision dependent variable, phygital is proven to be effective to the customer purchase decision. Since the offline store is already operating until now, what we need to do is to start signing up for a new online store as a new channel of Jaya Raya Store especially when today's era already has very advanced technology and also many businesses nowadays use technology and digital platforms to run their business.

The author recommended Jaya Raya Store to sign up for Tokopedia, Shopee, etc. as it is the largest digital platform marketplace in Indonesia. Digital Platform Marketplace is one channel that allows us to sell products through the internet and everyone will be able to come to the online store anytime that they want and have a leisure time to check every product that we sell. Even though usually most of the people would prefer come to the online store to be able to check on the product conditions before purchasing the product to avoid getting a broken product, the digital platform nowadays already has insurance to offer to make sure if the product purchased is broken when it arrived, the customer can always return the product with full refund and of course a proof of evidence is needed to proceed. Looking at the survey, the majority of the respondents also agree with these terms as it is already a common thing nowadays since many online stores applied these conditions as well.

Looking at the results of a survey conducted by the author, there are a number of things that must be taken into consideration in opening an online store, namely, not to differentiate goods sold in offline stores and online stores, stocks that must always be updated when selling online, allowing buyers to pick up their goods directly at the store. even though buying it online, and also provides a variety of payment methods so that customers can have the best choice to pay for the products they buy.

Optimizations of Digital Promotions by Using Social Media

According to the regression analysis of purchase decision dependent variable, Digital Promotions is proven to be effective to the customer purchase decision. Digital promotions mean to give promotions of the product we sell by using online media digital platforms. By using social media to optimize the spread of digital promotions, we can reach as many people as we want.

According to Pusparris (2021), Instagram is the favorite social media for generation Z, which is now around 16-23 years old, and the millennial generation with an age range of 24-37 years likes Whatsapp as their favorite social media. By spreading digital promotions through social media, this will also invite many people to come to social media to see promotions that are currently in effect, especially for promotion seekers.

Create An Attractive, Informative, and Neat Digital Catalog

According to the regression analysis of purchase decision dependent variable, digital catalog is proven to be effective to the customer purchase decision. Based on the respondent's answer from the digital catalog section and purchase decision section, digital catalogs must be well made, complete, informative, with clear photo displays, accessible by various devices and must always be updated with the latest version if there are changes. Purchase decision survey questionnaire results show that before potential

customers make a decision to buy a product, they tend to seek information about the product before buying it. Through this result, we can conclude that through an informative digital catalog, it can help convince potential customers to make a purchase decision to buy a product. The survey results have also stated that prospective buyers always compare a product with other products before buying, which means that if a digital catalog is able to provide a variety of products that can be compared with one another by listing the advantages and disadvantages of a product, then this digital catalog will really help potential customers to make a purchase decision to buy a product. The last one as a determinant of the purchase decision to buy a product is the price offered by Jaya Raya Store and the quality of the goods offered itself. Will require consideration of the price and goods to be sold in order to attract the attention of customers to encourage their purchase decision.

Implementation Plan

Implementation plan of the business solution from the subchapter above will be presented to Jaya Raya Store. This implementation plan consists of the action planning and the KPI of the plan integrated with a managed monthly schedule for 1 year. The plan can be started right away in January 2023 until December 2023. The table below will show us the implementation plan.

Table 9. Implementation Plan for Toko Jaya Raya

No.	Solution	Action Plan	Period
1	Advertise with Digital Catalog Through Digital Platform	Make new digital catalog banner for advertising	Every first week of the month
		Advertise to 10,000 users	First quarter of the year
		Review advertisement Engagement result	Every last week of the month.
		Keep trying to revise the advertisement criteria best on the best engagement	Every last week of the month
		Advertise to 20,000 users	Second quarter of the year
		Advertise to 40,000 users	Third quarter of the year
		Advertise to 80,000 users	Fourth quarter of the year
2	Sign up for every Possible Digital Platform Marketplace	Preparing to open online store products, display picture, product description, etc.	First month of the year
		Posting products to sell in the chosen digital marketplace	Second month of the year
		Set up new target sales for each digital marketplace	Every month
		Continuing sales from online shops	Every day
		Updating products stock	Every week
3	Optimization of Digital Promotions by using Social Media	Create Social Media Account	First month of the year.
		Posting digital promotions through story, feeds, etc.	Every week
		Limited monthly offering to potential customer	Every month
		Aim to have 50 repeat order customers	Every month
		Try interacting with customer through social media	Every day

4	Create an attractive, Informative, and Neat Digital Catalog	Create an attractive digital catalog	Every month
		Share digital catalog that has been made via social media or other digital platform	Every month
		Review digital catalog through survey	Every month
		Design digital catalog based on the survey, based on customer preference.	Every Month

All the action plans have been scheduled properly with different time period and need to be reviewed and monitored regularly. For every business solution proposed, there are many action plans that can be carried out to achieve the KPI of the solution.

CONCLUSION

Conclusion

Phyigital, Digital Promotions and Digital Catalog are considered to be the most effective channels for Jaya Raya Store. Phyigital which stands for both physical and digital at the same time are the methods that is currently being used by many UMKM businesses and looking at Jaya Raya Store condition, which only has physical channels, adding digital channels is the right step to be able to compete in this digital era. Digital promotions which are generally used by many businesses from various fields and seeing that Jaya Raya Store has never taken advantage of this, this is a good opportunity to start upgrading promotional channels to be more modern. Digital catalog as a channel which can introduce products sold to potential customers through an attractive catalog display. According to the research survey analysis done by the author, they are considered to be effective because the regression analysis result showed that they are affecting customer awareness and customer purchase decisions. The author hoped that by implementing the implementation plan provided, later increasing customer awareness and purchase decisions as a result can increase significant profits for Jaya Raya Store to overcome the post-pandemic situation.

The channel proposed for Jaya Raya Store can work well by applying the business solution and implementation plan proposed for Jaya Raya Store. The business solutions and implementation were made by using the analysis as a foundation. By considering Jaya Raya Store current conditions which is the lack of business channels, the author created 4 business solutions to be offered for the stakeholders to Jaya Raya Store which are advertise with digital catalog through digital platforms, sign up for every digital platform marketplace, optimization of digital promotions by using social media, and create an attractive, informative, and neat digital catalog.

The most effective combination of the proposed channels is in the first business solution which is by advertising with digital catalog through digital platform. Digital platforms are a very broad and unlimited field which can be used to carry out effective advertising as advertising is one of the factors in the promotion mix. This business solution utilizes more than 1 channel as a solution by utilizing digital platforms, digital promotions, social media, and digital catalogs simultaneously. By utilizing every possible channel, it is hoped that the results obtained will be maximized.

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